

Focus Group Schedule

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Conceptual Feedback on OSCAR

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<http://oscar-ai.eu/>

Logistics

Sample: maximum of 14 people, 7 junior researchers and 7 senior researchers. If possible from different fields of study.

Duration: 1:30 hours

Pre-requisites: none

Location: Video-conferencing

Procedure

1. *Welcome (10min)* - Focus Group Leaders will welcome the group, present themselves and ask for a quick presentation of each person in the group (e.g. name, institution and field of study).

2. *Quick presentation of the OSCAR project (5min)* - Focus Group Leaders will briefly present the OSCAR project and explain the objectives of the focus group that is happening. there will be two types of groups, i.e., one group of people that will integrate the three focus groups, and three groups of people that will do only one of the levels, the FG Leaders shall introduce this note accordingly.

3. *Discussion (60min)* - The group will be split into two small groups and will be asked to answer three questions that are defined in the user case below (20min for each question).

4. *Gather up (10min)* - Rejoin the groups and ask each group to explain their conclusions to all. There is the possibility to promote discussion between participants.

5. *Close-up (5min)* - Close the session and ask for a take-away word/message that will be collected using a word cloud collection software.

User case part 1

John is in his last year of his PhD student, on biological engineering.

During the past weeks John has been feeling anxious and stressed. He feels overwhelmed with the amount of work he still needs to finish and sometimes he wishes his supervisor would support him more. Additionally, he also has been thinking about what the next step for his career should be. He understands it would be important for him to learn how to manage his stress and how to plan his career.

Question 1: How should John start to address his challenges?

*This question will be asked before conceptually explaining the system. We want to know if the answers will match the system that we created.

User case part 2

John found an open-learning system. This system recommends specific content based on the learner's preferences and learning goals. It recommends a learning path - new skills the learner can potentially acquire, and that is updated by an algorithmic reasoning based on experts' suggestions of contents as well as individuals' usage of the system. The system also allows for an assessment, as a way to track the learner's progress.

*In order to conceptually explain the system, the group leaders will also show a flow graph (nao sei se há outro nome melhor para isto...) of the system.

Question 2: What are the benefits and challenges of this system?

User case part 3

Within the system, John also found that it is possible to request a mentor, who is someone that has expertise on the topic that John is aiming to learn and who also has experience working in academia. During the mentorship relation John will be suggested to engage with specific skills, topics or contents that already exist in the system.

Question 3: How can a mentor/mentee relationship be useful in such a system?